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WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN TEACHERS IN MATRICULATION SCHOOLS – AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

Human beings don't have just one drive, but many drives and needs. And to have a sense of wellbeing, these needs need to be met adequately. Work is very important as it gives a lot of meaning in life, but life is bigger than work. When our lives are only about work, the ability to meet other needs goes very low which results in frustration. When human beings get older, they have a sense of some control and mastery over their environment, as they maintain some boundaries and a structure – that they have set apart time for various things in their lives. "But once a person allows the need for work to be met at the expense of other needs, the sense of wellbeing and confidence go away. This research is a study to know about the matriculation school teachers work life balance.

Keywords:

Work Life Balance, Women, Teachers, Matriculation School Teachers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The expression was first used in the late 1970s to describe the balance between an individual's work and personal life. In the United States, this phrase was first used in 1986. Nearly three decades after the term was first used, work-life balance could well stump employers in India. Over the past twenty-five years, there has been a substantial increase in work which is felt to be due, in part, by information technology and by an intense, competitive work environment. Long-term loyalty and a "sense of corporate community" have been eroded by a performance culture that expects more and more from their employees yet offers little security in return. Many experts predicted that technology would eliminate most household chores and provide people with much more time to enjoy leisure activities; but many ignore this option, encouraged by prevailing consumerist culture and a political agenda that has "elevated the work ethic to unprecedented heights and thereby reinforced the low value and worth attached to parenting".

A result of work-life imbalance can be seen in a survey on career couples by Team Lease in February 2008. It showed that 54 percent of the respondents felt they were merely “weekend parents”. In addition, 34 percent of the working couples surveyed felt that since there were two careers the chances of a divorce were high. Moreover, most participants agreed that working in odd shift hours had a bearing on their marital relationships.

The mid-career professionals are most prone to having work-life imbalance. “Since they have already worked for some years, they begin to realise that they have only finite time while they have yet a lot to do and they have not reached the position they desire. This crisis often leads to a tendency to overwork to achieve things faster, and the work-life balance gets disturbed. The work-life balance is also essential for the professional growth of a person.

NEED FOR BALANCE

Peter Ellwood, chairman of a unique U.K.-based advocacy group, Employers for Work-Life Balance, believes that work-life balance is more crucial at this point in time than ever before. “Demographic and societal changes, globalisation and advances in technology are forcing business to transform the way they operate. Work-life balance strategies are a valuable tool in this transformation. They offer a win-win situation, engaging employees on the basis that there is ‘something in it for them’ too, and humanising the process of change,” he says.

The lobby defines work-life balance as thus: It is about people having a measure of control over when, where and how they work. It is achieved when an individual’s right to a fulfilled life inside and outside paid work is accepted and respected as the norm, to the mutual benefit of the individual, business and society

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Abigail Gregory and Susan Milner (2009) They conclude that forming rights, for example to parental leave and working time reduction, in a gender neutral way can represent a way forward for men and for women and help to rebalance the gender division of labour.

According to a position paper published by Caux Round Table and written by David Rodbourne in 1996, “while many leading US companies have extensive work life program policies and practices, most have not yet chanced their organizational cultures to support employees and managers who want to use work life options”.

A 1995 study, conducted to identify the reason why 67% of Extensions country based professional staff voluntarily left Ohio State University Extension between January, 1990 and December 31, 1994 (Roshan, 1995). The research found that the majority of program staff left the organization for the following reasons.

- Organisational factors, including low pay, too many work responsibilities, too many requirements, for advancement and lack of recognition for a job well done.
- Non work related factors, including family obligations, more money elsewhere, conflict with personal responsibilities and not time for personal relationships.

- Individual work related factors, including other priorities in life, too many late night meetings and conflict with others.

According to Jim Bird (1980) It is not an either or question, and looking as it is what has hurt both its advocates and the businesses who are trying to address it is not a case of – do we address work life balance and increase costs and decrease profits? Or do we increase profits and not address work life balance? The “right” work life programs definitely offer a competitive advantage in recruiting retention productivity and customer service levels and as result profitability. Work life balance programs are definitely competitive advantage.

In India Lahiri and Srivatsava (1976) had found out from their study in one of the industries that extrinsic rewards are more important to the workers, whereas Dayal and Sharma (1975) in another similar study carried out still another industry concluded that intrinsic rewards are more important to the workers, In another study Dayal says that Indian labour prefer paternalistic approach of management, while Srivatsava contradictorily says that workers would like to participate in decision making give an opportunity, based on one of his studies.

Three persons, Jeffrey H. Greenhaus, Karen M. Collins, Jason D. Shaw examined the relation between work family balance and quality of life among professionals employed in public accounting. Three components of work family balance were assessed: Time balance (equal time devoted to work and family), involvement balance (equal involvement in work and family), satisfaction balance (equal satisfaction with work and family). For individuals who invested substantial time in their combined work and the family roles, those who spent more time on family than work experience a higher quality of life than balanced individuals who, in turn, experienced a higher quality of life than those who spent more time on work than family.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is a descriptive research. Primary data was collected with the help of structured questionnaire in two Matriculation Schools in Palayamkottai. A total of 35 respondents were taken to carry out this research. The researcher adopted convenient sampling method for the research. A pilot study was conducted with 5 respondents for testing the validity of the questionnaire and necessary addition and deletions were made in the questionnaire. Using statistical package for social science, various tools like simple regressions, one-way ANOVA were administered. Based on the test results, some of the findings were derived.

Table 1: One Way ANOVA

To analyses whether there is any significant difference in affected children and working hours of the respondents, the following hypotheses are framed and ANOVA test is applied.

H₀: There is no association between the affected children and working hours of the respondents.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Results
Between Groups	4.606	12	.384	2.235	0.47	Significant

Within Groups	3.950	23	.172			
Total	8.556	35				

The above table reveals that the calculated 'F' value (0.905) is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance. Therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is association between the affected children and working hours of the respondents.

Table 2: Simple Regression

Hypothesis is being tested using simple regressions.

Hypothesis Not enough time with family and sum of work family conflict can predict the impact of work life balance of teachers in matriculation schools.

Regression analysis is used to assess the relationship between one dependent variable (DV) and one independent variable (IV). This is the most commonly used technique in much of the social science research.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.505	.455	.347		1622.815

INFERENCE

The above model summary table shows R-Square for this model is 0.455. This means that 45.5 percent of the variation in overall satisfaction from work life balance (dependent variable) can be explained from the independent variables. The table also shows the adjusted R-Square for the model as 0.347

Table 3: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Co-efficient		Standardized Co- efficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std.Error	Beta		
1 (constant)					
Not enough time	1970.963	297.876		6.617	.000
	.079	.014	.505	5.5755	.000

a) Dependent Variable: Sum of work family conflict

INFERENCE

The table 3 shows standardized co-efficient for this model is Beta .505 and the 't' value 5.5755, which indicates that the variables are unrelated and the significant level .000 indicate that there is significant relationship among the variables. The table concluded that, enough time with family and sum of work family conflict can predict the impact of work life balance of teachers in Matriculation Schools.

4. CONCLUSION

The study investigates the work life balance of Teachers in matriculation schools. The findings throw light on some factors that play a significant role in determining work – life balance of teachers. The teachers feel that these factors are trouble them a lot to balance their work and life. The factors are not keeping their health fit and spending time in children, not getting enough sleep and eat. “Real success is finding your lifework in the work that you love” -David McCullough. Hence, the teachers working in the matriculation schools seem to be somewhat satisfied and are able to balance their work and life.

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